

Evaluation of the Corrosion Resistance of NiCr and Cr₂C based Coating in Stimulated Boiler Environment

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ABSTRACT

Traditional steels and their alloys cannot resist corrosion in the boilers of thermal power plants at high temperatures. Due to higher working temperatures for boilers, the problems of hot corrosion have grown more upfront. Several researchers have recently attempted to use surface coatings to reduce the boiler steels corroding in the heat. These dissimilar layer methods consume demonstrated to improve boiler steel material resistance to corrosion and boost their efficiency at high functioning temperatures, therefore expanding their lifespan. The advance of new exterior coatings through exceedingly superior decomposition resistance properties is the consequence of these developments in the field of coatings and advancements in thermal spraying processes as well as the different composite coating powders available at present.

Keywords: *Corrosion*, Porosity, Mechanical properties, Microstructure, Thermal spray.

1. Introduction

Steels and other materials go through a variety of working situations at high temperatures. Corrosion is an issue as a result of using steels in this high-temperature application. Steels and other materials go through a variety of working situations at high temperatures. Corrosion is an issue as a result of using steels in this high-temperature application. The oxidation of material at high temperatures that's what allows boiler steel to corrode. The contaminants in the coal used in the boilers encompass oxide of vanadium, sodium, and sulphur. These contaminants combine with oxygen to form oxides, which can corrode metals¹.

Sulphur and oxygen combines to form SO₂, which just slightly oxidises to produce SO₃. When sodium and vanadium react with oxygen, they produce sodium and vanadium oxides.. These oxides combine toward procedure multifaceted oxides of V and Na, which are popularly recognized as vanadates². The term " heated rusting " refers to hot corrosion that has been accelerated because of salt³.

Impurities such as V₂O₅ and NaCl, combined to produce deposits which are molten that damage the protective coatings. In systems for producing energy, leftover fuel oil and coal are frequently used due to the lack of high-quality fuels, as well as the reason for fiscal gain. These energies include contaminants that form composites on the material's surface at low melting points and will lead to decomposition. Such composites are usually named as Powder. The supposed powder deposits on the physical exterior and leads to hot decomposition. Substantial degeneration occurs when these liquefied composites liquefy the defensive oxide layers which are formed physically on the boiler materials during the gas turbine and boiler operation⁴⁻⁸. Many situations that resulted in fatalities and property damage were due to a failure to prevent or minimally sense heated rusting at an initial on phase. Tens of millions of dollars are frequently spent to restore deteriorated structures, machinery, and equipment in addition to the immediate expenses associated with shutdown and productivity loss. Moreover, abrupt material degradation can result in human handicaps or even risk to life^{9,10}. When boiler tubes and other parts are corroding, power plants may need to shut down. Boiler steam

temperature and thermal efficiency are both reduced by corrosion. Brittle erosion is the process of material loss brought on by crack development as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Representation of crack formation in single particle impact

Conventional steels, which are used extensively in thermal power plants, cannot tolerate corrosion issues. In recent years, scientists have improved the oxidation and hot corrosion protection of steel by using several types of coatings. These days, a lot of items are coated using thermal spray technology to strengthen their resistance to abrasive wear and prolong their usable lives.¹¹⁻¹⁴

In recent years, these coatings have become more considerable significance to recover the Boiler steel life duration at high temperature environment applications. Inventions in the powder and wire production in addition to improvements made to heat-based spraying coating strategies have produced the expansion of external coatings with strong confrontation against weathering and corrosion¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Such coating methods have no picky limitations in the core and surface composition¹⁸. Coatings of High-hardness at a few millimeters of thickness can be developed. High-velocity oxyfuel spraying, flame, arc, and plasma spraying methods are typically used to shield boiler components¹⁹. Due to the reason of The flame system is remelting not often cast-off, and the plasma coating technique is comparatively costly²⁰⁻²². In the current history, Various methods are used to thicken various coatings on boiler steels to improve corrosion resistance. The works of several research authors have been described in the following section.

2. Literature review

Prakash et al. [23] investigated the coating behaviour of Ni-50Cr cold spray coating on boiler steel. The substrates T-22 and SA 516 were coated using the cold spray spraying method. The outcomes underwent SEM/EDAX and XED analysis. The XED analysis shows that Ni forms as the primary phase for Ni-50Cr coating on T-22 and SA 516. Ni and Cr dominate the coating composition, leading to the development of Ni and Cr oxides, as seen by SEM/EDAX, while Fe_2O_3 formed in the untreated specimen, causing corrosion. For 50 cycles, the coated and uncoated specimens were inspected in the Na_2SO_4 -60% V_2O_5 molten salt environment. It was noted that the layered sampling exhibits no particle splinting, while the untreated samples had specimen porosities. As a result, the coating helps to prevent corrosion by preventing oxygen from diffusing into the substance.

Sidhu and Prakash [24] provided an illustration of how HVOF coatings strengthened the GrA1 ASTM-SA210 steel's resistance to heat oxidation and corrosion in the presence of molten salt deposits of Na_2SO_4 - V_2O_5 salts. On ASTM SA-210 GrA1 steel, metallic coatings such as Ni-Cr, WC-Co, Cr_3C_2 -NiCr, and satellite-6 have been dumped using the HVOF technique. LPG is the fuel gas utilised in this procedure. The surface qualities were determined by measuring the porosity. The

samples were subjected to molten salt at 900°C under cyclic conditions for hot corrosion research. NiCr coating was shown to be the most effective coating, followed by Cr₃C₂-NiCr coating. WC-Substrate was the least successful steel coating in stopping substrate corrosion. On the uncoated steel, severe spalling and scale peeling were seen as a result of heat corrosion.

The mechanical properties and microstructure of NiCr thermal spray coatings using Cr₃C₂, as well as their efficacy and suitability for use in various corrosion and erosion situations, were investigated in Chatha et al.'s study [25]. The Cr₃C₂-NiCr based coatings were mostly attacked through the gaps in the splat at the borders, which were created by the thermal spray coatings. Effective carbide coating deposition was standard practise for detonation techniques, plasma spray coating techniques and high velocity oxy fuel.

In a molten salt environment with 60% V₂O₅ and Na₂SO₄, Gond et al. [26] investigated the corrosion resistance behaviour of bare T-22 and T-91 steel at 900°C. The unprotected steel was placed in a molten salt environment with 25% NaCl and 75% Na₂SO₄. The data was analysed using a variety of methods, such as weight change analysis, x-ray diffraction analysis, and energy dispersive analysis. It was found that T-91 steel provided better protection against hot corrosion than T-22 steel because the latter had a thin coating of loosely organised and less protective NiO. However, as a result of the XRD approach, T-91 steel developed a layer of chromium oxide on its surface that serves as a barrier against heat corrosion. Furthermore, enormous, deep holes occurred in T-22 steel, whereas relatively tiny ones formed in T-91 steel. As a result, it was found that T-91 steel outperformed T-22 steel in a molten salt environment of 75wt%Na₂SO₄+25wt%NaCl. Figure 2 shows the most likely mechanism of corrosion assault for this Ni–20Cr-coated on bare T11 steel subjected to a molten salt environment containing 60% V₂O₅ and Na₂SO₄ at 900°C for 50 cycles.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram showing probable hot corrosion mechanism for Ni–20Cr-coated T11 steel exposed to Na₂SO₄–60%V₂O₅ at 900°C for 50 cycles

The high temperature and oxidation resistance of Ni-20Cr and Ni-50Cr coatings on SAE 213 T22 bare steel at 900°C for 50 cycles under cyclic settings were studied by Bala et al. [27] using a boiler scenario simulation model. It was shown that oxidation in the air and salt conditions for 50 cycles at 900°C in the simulated scenario caused uncoated steel to accumulate greater weight. The Ni-Cr coating was showing a higher resistance to corrosion in the simulated environment.

The corrosion resistance of FeCr and NiCr coatings for the burning of biomass was studied by Varis et al. [28] under simplified conditions. The coatings were applied to the substrate material using a high velocity oxy fuel thermal spraying method. As biomass ash, the researchers employed a synthetic salt combination of KCl and K₂SO₄. After applying this biomass ash to the coated material, it was heated in two separate gas chamber atmospheres for 168 hours at 550°C and 600°C, respectively. It had been observed that at 550°C, neither the chromium content of the applied coatings nor the amount of chlorine leaking through them reduced. At 600°C, significant chromium depletion was seen in both ambient and humid conditions. It has been discovered that Fe-based HVOF CJS Fe25Cr coatings exhibit strong corrosion resistance; yet, no chlorine penetration was seen throughout this coating.

Fernandez et al. [29] specifically contrasted the end results with coatings sprayed with Ni-Cr plasma on AISI stainless bare steel. The investigation looked at the corrosion of laser-treated Cr-N base coatings at 773 K and 1073 K temperatures, respectively, inside a steam production boiler with 3.5 volume percent free oxygen. Using a laser approach, the authors combined Ni base alloy pearl production with all plasma spray coating. The application of laser treatment has resulted in reduced porosity and a uniform coating.

Under actual boiler circumstances, Singh and Singh [30] observed corrosion of Al₂O₃-coated T-91 bare boiler steel. The powder coating method of detonation cannon thermal spraying has been utilised for Al₂O₃. The samples that are coated and those that are not show recurrent conditions. It was found that the degradation of the scale from the samples was the reason for the 2.96 percent weight loss in coated T-91. It was found that Al₂O₃-coated T-91 steel offered a higher erosion-corrosion danger under real-world conditions than did T-91 bare steel.

Somasundaram et al. [31] combined Cr₃C₂-35% NiCr powder with Si alloy products to make a composite powder. The composite powder was applied to three distinct boiler steel types (SA213-T22, MDN-310, and Superfer 800H) using a high velocity oxy fuel method. Under these conditions, the coated steels were subjected to air oxidation at 700°C on many occasions. The coating demonstrated improved resistance to corrosion caused by oxidation. The creation of oxides of Cr₂O₃, SiO₂, and spinels such as NiCr₂O₄ and Ni₂(SiO₄) led to the superior resistance of the Cr₃C₂-35% NiCr+5% Si coating to oxidation, as revealed by the results of the XRD technique. At the substrate-coating interface, oxygen was not evident, suggesting that the coating surface had not been contacted by oxidising agents. On boiler bare steel, various carbon nanotube mixes with zirconium yttrium coatings were applied, and corrosion behaviour at 600°C was observed under cyclic conditions. The authors used the air plasma spraying method to deposit the coating particles. The uncoated steel experienced severe corrosion and spallation due to the iron oxides. The corrosion resistance rose when zirconium yttrium coatings and carbon nanotubes were mixed. The improvement in corrosion resistance was mostly caused by the formation of zirconium oxides in the scale and the homogeneous dispersion of carbon nanotubes in the coating medium.

In Wang et al.'s work [32], the effect on the performance of WC-Co coating was investigated using a detonation gun spraying separation device. The outcomes demonstrated that the WC-Co coatings sprayed using a D-gun were enhanced by the separation system. Moreover, even though the porosity of the coatings had been restricted, it was still permitted.

The effectiveness of TiO₂ and Ni₃Al coatings on boiler bare steel T-91 at 900°C was examined by Singh et al. [33]. The HVOF coating method was used to the details. Following coating, the specimens were subjected to 50 cycles of 900°C and a molten salt environment (Na₂SO₄-60% V₂O₅). The cycles included a 20-minute cooling period after an hour-long heating phase. An experiment was conducted to track the behaviour of HVOF sprayed coatings and the rate of corrosion using X-ray Diffraction (XRD), SEM/EDS, and thermogravimetric techniques. The XRD test findings showed that Fe₂O₃, Cr₂O₃, and Fe₃O₄ were the dominant phases. The efficacy of Ni₃Al and TiO₂ coatings on T-91 boiler bare steel at 900°C. The specifications were coated using the HVOF method. Following coating, the specimens were subjected to 50 cycles of 900°C and a molten salt environment (Na₂SO₄-60% V₂O₅). The cycles comprised a heating phase lasting an hour and a cooling phase lasting twenty minutes. In an experiment, the behaviour of coatings and the rate of corrosion were evaluated using the SEM/EDS, X-ray diffraction (XRD), and thermogravimetric techniques. The results of the XRD test indicated that the oxides of Fe₂O₃, Cr₂O₃, and Fe₃O₄ were the most prevalent phases.

Two thermally sprayed HVOF coatings, Fe-27Cr-11Ni-4Mo and Fe-19Cr-9W-7Nb-4Mo, were tested for their ability to inhibit corrosion on carbon steel tubes (St35.8, DIN 17175-79, diameter 38/5.5 mm) by Oksa et al. [34]. The coatings that were being evaluated were subjected to boiler conditions for a period of two years. In the 20 μm outer layer, there was some minor corrosion visible on the Fe-19Cr coating. A few perpendicular fractures and the covering's restricted porosity allowed corrosion to seep to the surface. The researchers came to the conclusion that, in the given conditions, the Fe-27Cr HVOF coating demonstrated a significant resistance to corrosion. Numerous features of the hot corrosion process change as it moves from the Initiation phase to the Propagation phase, as shown in Figure 3.

HOT CORROSION CHRONOLOGY

Figure 3: Initiation and propagation stages of high temperature corrosion

The corrosion behaviour of iron-based superalloys covered with Cr₃C₂-NiCr and subjected to heat corrosion was assessed by Kamal et al. [35]. The specimens were subjected to the corrosive effects

of Na_2SO_4 at 900°C for 100 cycles. A detonation gun was used to spray the coating. A molten salt environment was used to evaluate the hot corrosion behaviour of coated and bare steels using XRD, SEM, FE-SEM/EDAX, and thermogravimetric methods. The resistance to heat corrosion was improved in the Cr_3C_2 -NiCr coating. However, in contrast to Superni 75 and 718, Super alloy 800H shown a higher level of resistance to heat corrosion. The D-gun spraying method was used to develop the Cr_3C_2 -NiCr coating, which reduced porosity and resulted in homogenous small grains and flat splat forms.

In a molten salt environment, Kaur et al. [36] examined the corrosion resistance behaviour of the Cr_3C_2 -NiCr coating on T-22 steel. The base material was coated using the D spray technique. Both coated and naked steel specimens were exposed to fifteen cycles of exposure, followed by a one-hour cooling period at room temperature following a hundred hours of heating in a boiler environment at 700°C . To get the data, four methods were employed: cross-sectional analysis, XRD technique, weight change method, and SEM/EDS method. Scale spalling and weight increase were seen in uncoated specimens, but coated specimens showed no change in weight growth and no spallation.

In a real boiler that was subjected to cyclic thermal loading and heated to 900°C , Goyal et al.'s study [37] examined the hot corrosion behavior of carbon nanotube-modified chromium oxide composite coatings. The coatings were applied using a high-velocity oxy-fuel technique, with a CNT concentration ranging from 1 to 8 weight percent. The scientists found that the carbon nanotubes filled in the cracks, voids, and microscopic holes in the coating microstructure, acting as a physical barrier against the species responsible for corrosion. The coatings had reduced weight growth and formed protective oxide scales during the course of the testing. Reduced hot corrosion rates were linked to higher CNT content in the coating matrix.

Singh et al. [38] coated T11 and P91 bare boiler steels with Ni-Cr and Cr_3C_2 -NiCr using the detonation gun spray coating process. They then monitored the steels' reactions to heat corrosion in a genuine boiler simulation setting. The investigators found that out of all the specimens, the uncoated boiler steel specimens lost the most weight. The Cr_3C_2 -NiCr coating outperformed the Ni-Cr coating because the Cr_2C_3 , Cr_3O_2 , Cr_3Fe , and Cr_3Ni_2 phases occur in a true boiler environment and are resistant to heat corrosion.

In a 700°C simulated molten salt environment, Singh et al. [39] examined the hot corrosion behaviours of various Cr_3C_2 -NiCr coatings on boiler bare tube steel. The microstructures of the corroded specimens were analysed by elemental composition analysis and X-ray diffraction. When compared to coatings made of $20\text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2$ -80NiCr, 100NiCr, and $35\text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2$ -65NiCr, they discovered that $10\text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2$ -90NiCr and its coating had the best corrosion resistance. The coated surface developed a layer of chromium carbide, which prevented corrosion.

Rehman et al. [40] developed the Triballoy T-900 wear-resistance coating alloy, which is mechanically alloyed with aluminium and yttrium. At 900°C , the researchers looked at how modified and untreated metals behaved when hot corrosion occurred. The results of the experiments showed that coatings covered with yttrium and aluminium had the best resistance to heat corrosion. Significant hot corrosion attack was seen on unaltered coatings as a result of molybdenum oxide synthesis, less stable NiO in the salt breaking down, and the resulting development of sulphide. Al_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 layers were created as a result of the Yttrium addition's selective oxidation of Al and Cr. The region was shielded from the attack of the molten salt by the oxide layer.

In a molten salt $V_2O_5+45\text{wt}\% Na_2SO_4$ environment at 900°C , Kadhim et al. [41] investigated the hot corrosion behaviours of a moderately stabilised zirconia alumina composite coating on stainless steel 316L specimens that were left naked. The outcomes showed that YSZ/ Al_2O_3 composite coatings outperform traditional YSZ sprayed coatings in terms of hot corrosion resistance. The yttria degeneration from the zirconia yttria coatings was identified as the cause of the YSZ deterioration. Al_2O_3 was used in the composite coating to reduce porosity and increase corrosion resistance by filling in the voids and cracks in the YSZ coating.

Recently, some authors have combined nanomaterials 42–46 with coatings made of nanocrystalline metal matrices such alumina, titanium dioxide, and silicon carbide. The corrosion resistance was improved by the inclusion of nanoparticles. When Ni, Ni-W, or Ni-Co alloys are combined with SiC nanoparticles, researchers have seen an increase in corrosion resistance 47–49. After applying nickel coatings containing Al_2O_3 nanoparticles to steel, the steel's resistance to corrosion was assessed in a solution of molten salt. Al_2O_3 was shown to act as an insulator on the composite surface, where a slightly greater resistivity was seen in the NaCl solution 50. Corrosive elements 51 were kept out of the nickel grains by the Al_2O_3 nanoparticles refining them.

Because of their superior mechanical behaviour and increased resistance to wear and corrosion, metal nitride films are widely employed as protective coatings 52. These coatings have the benefit of being able to function at temperatures beyond 700°C because, in high-temperature applications, they do not degrade into porous oxides at the film surface 53. Coatings based on Cr and Ni are well recognised for offering remarkable resistance to oxidation and wear at temperatures as high as 900°C 54–55. Because of its increased coating density, condensed coating roughness, and decreased connection porosity, a multilayer system based on Cr and Ni offers better corrosion resistance 56. It should be mentioned that Cr-based nitride coatings have superior strength and oxidation resistance than Ti-based nitrides, which makes them more appropriate for use in high-temperature applications.

When coated with wear-resistant powders, medium carbon steel, which finds usage in agricultural applications, can assist extend the component's service life, according to research by Jimmy Metha et al. [57]. Figure 4 shows the Hipojet 2700 equipment used for HVOF spraying. The detonation cannon spray approach was employed because of its low porosity, high density, and wear-resistant qualities. Using ball milling, two distinct compositions were made from tungsten carbide, cobalt, and nickel-chromium carbide combined with rare earth elements. I WC-CO + 5% CeO_2 , II WC-CO + 10% CeO_2 , III Cr_3C_2 -NiCr + 5% CeO_2 , and IV Cr_3C_2 NiCr + 10% CeO_2 were the four compositions that were created. One of the main uses for boron steel is in agricultural settings, where wear is a prevalent issue. Three distinct load scenarios were tested for wear using the pin-on-disc test equipment. With the use of XRD technology, worn-out surface phase identification was accomplished. Therefore, it was determined that when the applied stress is low, WC-Co with a high rare earth addition exhibits minimal wear rate loss and, consequently, insignificant volume rate loss.

Figure 4: Hipojet 2700 propellant

3. Conclusions

The following findings are reached after reviewing previous research on the high-temperature corrosion behaviours of thermal spray coatings:

1. A review of the literature reveals that several researchers have created a range of coatings using thermal spraying techniques to improve the hot corrosion resistance of steels used in the boiler and mining sectors.
2. Researchers used thermal spraying, HVOFing, air plasma spraying, cold spraying, and D-gun spraying to develop hard coatings that increased corrosion resistance.
3. Even with the most sophisticated and intricate coating techniques, it is difficult to produce coatings free of flaws since thermal spray coatings are porous in nature and have a lot of local microcracks or through pores.
4. The porosities and fissures also contribute to the coatings' decreased hardness. These voids/porosities make the substrate alloy susceptible to attack by corrosive agents. The coating's surface roughness rises and its hardness reduces due to its high porosity. It is the main reason why thermal spray coatings fail.
5. To enhance the hot corrosion resistance of boiler steels used in the mining and boiler industries at high operating temperatures, more research is needed to decrease the porosity and raise the hardness of the coatings.
6. For thermal power plants and the mining sector, hot corrosion of boiler steels at high-temperature working conditions is a major issue.

4. References

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